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Abstract:

In this paper, the notions of $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - interval valued fuzzy subnear-rings, $(\in, \in \vee q)$ -interval valued fuzzy ideal and $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - interval valued fuzzy quasi-ideal of near-rings are studied. The characterization of such $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - interval valued fuzzy ideals are also obtained.

Key Words: Interval-Valued Fuzzy Subnear Ring, Fuzzy Ideal & Quasi-Ideal

1. Introduction:

The theory of fuzzy set which was introduced by Zadeh[20] is applied to many Mathematical branches. The notion of fuzzy subgroup was introduced by Rosenfeld[17] in 1971. Fuzzy ideals and rings were introduced by W.Liu[13] and it has been studied by several authors[9,11,12]. The notions of fuzzy subnear-rings, fuzzy ideals of near-rings were introduced by Salah Abou-Zaid[18], A.L. Narayanan introduced the notion of fuzzy quasi-ideal of near-rings. A new type of fuzzy subgroup (viz, $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - fuzzy subgroup) was introduced in an earlier paper of Bhakat and Das[1] by using the combined notions of "belonginess" and "quasicoincidence" of fuzzy points and fuzzy sets. The concept has been studied further in[1,2,3,4,5]. As a generalization of fuzzy set Zadeh[20] in 1975 introduced a new notion of fuzzy subsets viz., interval valued (i-v) fuzzy subset, where the values of the membership function are closed intervals of numbers instead of a number. Thillai govindan et.al.,[19] introduced the notion of i-v fuzzy subnear-ring and i-v fuzzy left (right) ideal of near-ring and investigated some of their properties. Further Chinnadurai and Kadalarasi[6] studied interval valued fuzzy quasi-ideal of near-rings. In this paper, we extend the i-v fuzzy set notion to $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - fuzzy subnear-rings and $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - fuzzy ideals of near-rings.

2. Preliminaries:

We first recall some basic concepts for the sake of completeness. By a near-ring [10] we mean a non-empty set N with two binary operations '+' and '.' satisfying the following axioms:

- (i) $(N, +)$ is a group,
- (ii) $(N, \cdot)$ is a semigroup,
- (iii) $(x + y) \cdot z = x \cdot z + y \cdot z \forall x, y, z \in N$.

Precisely speaking, it is a right near-ring because it satisfies the right distributive law. We will use the word "near-ring" to mean "right near-ring". We denote xy instead of $x \cdot y$. Note that $0x = 0$ but in general $x0 \neq 0$ for some $x \in N$. If P and Q are two non-empty subsets of N we define $PQ = \{ab / a \in P, b \in Q\}$ and $P^*Q = \{a(b+i) - ab / a, b \in P, i \in Q\}$.

A subgroup M of a near-ring N is called a subnear-ring of N if $MM \subseteq M$.

A near-ring N is called zero-symmetric if $x0 = 0 \forall x \in N$. A subset I of a near-ring N is called an ideal of N if

- (i) $(I, +)$ is a normal subgroup of $(N, +)$,
- (ii) $IN \subseteq I$,
- (iii) $a(b+i) - ab \in I \forall a, b \in N$ and $i \in I$, that is, $N^*I \subseteq I$.

A normal subgroup R of $(N, +)$ with (ii) is called a right ideal of N while a normal subgroup L of $(N, +)$ with (iii) is called a left ideal of N . A subgroup Q of $(N, +)$ is called a quasi-ideal of near-ring N if $QN \cap NQ \cap N^*Q \subseteq Q$.

We now review some fuzzy logic concepts.

Definition 2.1 [19] An interval number $\bar{a}$ on $[0,1]$ is a closed subinterval of $[0,1]$, that is, $\bar{a} = [a^-, a^+]$ such that $0 \leq a^- \leq a^+ \leq 1$ where a^- and a^+ are the lower and upper end limits of $\bar{a}$ respectively. The set of all closed subintervals of $[0,1]$ is denoted by $D[0,1]$. We also identify the interval $[a, a]$ by the number $a \in [0,1]$. For any interval numbers

$\bar{a}_i = [a_i^-, a_i^+], \bar{b}_i = [b_i^-, b_i^+] \in D[0,1], i \in I$, we define

$$\max^i \{\bar{a}_i, \bar{b}_i\} = [\max^i \{a_i^-, b_i^-\}, \max^i \{a_i^+, b_i^+\}],$$

$$\min^i \{\bar{a}_i, \bar{b}_i\} = [\min^i \{a_i^-, b_i^-\}, \min^i \{a_i^+, b_i^+\}],$$

$$\inf^i \bar{a}_i = [\bigcap_{i \in I} a_i^-, \bigcap_{i \in I} a_i^+], \sup^i \bar{a}_i = [\bigcup_{i \in I} a_i^-, \bigcup_{i \in I} a_i^+]$$

In this notation $\bar{0} = [0, 0]$ and $\bar{1} = [1, 1]$. For any interval numbers $\bar{a} = [a^-, a^+]$ and $\bar{b} = [b^-, b^+]$ on $[0, 1]$, define

$$(1) \bar{a} \leq \bar{b} \text{ if and only if } a^- \leq b^- \text{ and } a^+ \leq b^+.$$

$$(2) \bar{a} = \bar{b} \text{ if and only if } a^- = b^- \text{ and } a^+ = b^+.$$

$$(3) \bar{a} < \bar{b} \text{ if and only if } \bar{a} \leq \bar{b} \text{ and } \bar{a} \neq \bar{b}$$

$$(4) k\bar{a} = [ka^-, ka^+], \text{ whenever } 0 \leq k \leq 1.$$

Definition 2.2 [19] Let X be any set. A mapping $\bar{A}: X \rightarrow D[0, 1]$ is called an interval-valued fuzzy subset (briefly, i-v fuzzy subset) of X where $D[0, 1]$ denotes the family of all closed subintervals of $[0, 1]$ and $\bar{A}(x) = [A^-(x), A^+(x)]$ for all $x \in X$, where A^- and A^+ are fuzzy subsets of X such that $A^-(x) \leq A^+(x)$ for all $x \in X$. Note that $\bar{A}(x)$ is an interval (a closed subset of $[0, 1]$) and not a number from the interval $[0, 1]$ as in the case of fuzzy subset.

Definition 2.3. [19] A mapping $\min^i: D[0, 1] \times D[0, 1] \rightarrow D[0, 1]$ defined by

$$\min^i(\bar{a}, \bar{b}) = [\min\{a^-, b^-\}, \min\{a^+, b^+\}] \text{ for all } \bar{a}, \bar{b} \in D[0, 1] \text{ is called an interval min-norm.}$$

Definition 42.4. [19] A mapping $\max^i: D[0, 1] \times D[0, 1] \rightarrow D[0, 1]$ defined by

$$\max^i(\bar{a}, \bar{b}) = [\max\{a^-, b^-\}, \max\{a^+, b^+\}] \text{ for all } \bar{a}, \bar{b} \in D[0, 1] \text{ is called an interval max-norm.}$$

Let $\min^i$ and $\max^i$ be the interval min-norm and max-norm on $D[0, 1]$ respectively. Then the following are true.

$$1. \min^i\{\bar{a}, \bar{a}\} = \bar{a} \text{ and } \max^i\{\bar{a}, \bar{a}\} = \bar{a} \text{ for all } \bar{a} \in D[0, 1].$$

$$2. \min^i\{\bar{a}, \bar{b}\} = \min^i\{\bar{b}, \bar{a}\} \text{ and } \max^i\{\bar{a}, \bar{b}\} = \max^i\{\bar{b}, \bar{a}\} \text{ for all } \bar{a}, \bar{b} \in D[0, 1].$$

3. If $\bar{a} \geq \bar{b} \in D[0, 1]$, then $\min^i\{\bar{a}, \bar{c}\} \geq \min^i\{\bar{b}, \bar{c}\}$ and $\max^i\{\bar{a}, \bar{c}\} \geq \max^i\{\bar{b}, \bar{c}\}$ for all $\bar{c} \in D[0, 1]$. Let $\bar{A}$ and $\bar{B}$ be two i-v fuzzy subsets of semigroup X . We define the relation $\subseteq$ between $\bar{A}$ and $\bar{B}$, the intersection and product of $\bar{A}$ and $\bar{B}$, respectively as follows:

$$(i) \bar{A} \subseteq \bar{B} \text{ if } \bar{A}(x) \leq \bar{B}(x) \forall x \in X,$$

$$(ii) (\bar{A} \cap \bar{B})(x) = \min^i\{\bar{A}(x), \bar{B}(x)\} \forall x \in X,$$

$$(iii) (\bar{A} \circ \bar{B})(x) = \begin{cases} \sup_{x=yz}^i [\min^i\{\bar{A}(y), \bar{B}(z)\}] & \text{if } x = yz, \text{ for } y, z \in X, \\ \bar{0} & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases}$$

It is easily verified that the "product" of i-v fuzzy subsets is associative. Throughout this paper, N will denote a near-ring unless otherwise specified.

Definition 52.5. [19] For an i-v fuzzy subset $\bar{A}$ of a set X and $\bar{t} \in D[0, 1]$, the subset $\bar{A}_{\bar{t}} = \{x \in X / \bar{A}(x) \geq \bar{t}\}$ is called a level subset of X determined by $\bar{A}$ and $\bar{t}$.

Definition 6 2.6. [19] An i-v fuzzy subset $\bar{A}$ of a set X of the form

$$\bar{A}(y) = \begin{cases} \bar{t} (\neq \bar{0}) & \text{if } y = x, \\ \bar{0} & \text{if } y \neq x \end{cases}$$

is said to be an i-v fuzzy point with support x and value $\bar{t}$ and is denoted by $x_{\bar{t}}$.

Definition 7 2.7. [19] An i-v fuzzy subset $\bar{A}$ of a group G is said to be an i-v fuzzy subgroup of G if $\forall x, y \in G$, (i) $\bar{A}(xy) \geq \min^i\{\bar{A}(x), \bar{A}(y)\}$, (ii) $\bar{A}(x^{-1}) \geq \bar{A}(x)$.

Definition 8 2.8. [19] An i-v fuzzy subset $\bar{A}$ of N is called an i-v fuzzy subnear-ring of N if $\forall x, y \in N$, (i) $\bar{A}(x - y) \geq \min^i\{\bar{A}(x), \bar{A}(y)\}$, (ii) $\bar{A}(xy) \geq \min^i\{\bar{A}(x), \bar{A}(y)\}$.

Definition 9 2.9. [19] An i-v fuzzy subset $\bar{A}$ of N is said to be an i-v fuzzy ideal of N if

(i) $\bar{A}$ is an i-v fuzzy subnear-ring of N . (ii) $\bar{A}(y+x-y) \geq \bar{A}(x) \forall x, y \in N$,

(iii) $\bar{A}(xy) \geq \bar{A}(x) \forall x, y \in N$, (iv) $\bar{A}(a(b+i)-ab) \geq \bar{A}(i) \forall a, b, i \in N$.

An i-v fuzzy subset with (i), (ii) and (iii) is called an i-v fuzzy right ideal of N whereas an i-v fuzzy subset with (i), (ii) and (iv) is called an i-v fuzzy left ideal of N .

Definition 10 2.10. [19] Let $\bar{A}$ be an i-v fuzzy subset of N . We define

$$(N * \bar{A})(x) = \begin{cases} \sup_{x=a(b+i)-ab} \bar{A}(i) & \text{if } x = a(b+i)-ab, a, b, i \in N, \\ \bar{0} & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Definition 11 2.11. [19] An i-v fuzzy subgroup $\bar{A}$ of N is called an i-v fuzzy quasi-ideal of N if $(\bar{A} \circ N) \cap (N \circ \bar{A}) \cap (N * \bar{A}) \subseteq \bar{A}$.

Example 2.12.12 Let $N = \{0, a, b, c\}$ be the near-ring with $(N, +)$ as the Klein's four group and $(N, \cdot)$ as defined below

+	0	a	b	c
0	0	a	b	c
a	a	0	c	b
b	b	c	0	a
c	c	b	a	0

·	0	a	b	c
0	0	0	0	0
a	a	a	a	a
b	0	0	0	b
c	a	a	a	c

Let $Q = \{0, c\}$. Then $QN = \{0, a, c\}$, $NQ = \{0, a, b, c\}$ and $N * Q = \{0, b\}$.

Therefore $QN \cap NQ \cap N * Q = \{0\} \subseteq Q$. Hence Q is a quasi-ideal of N .

Define an i-v fuzzy subset $\bar{A}: N \rightarrow D[0,1]$ by $\bar{A}(0) = \bar{A}(c) = \bar{1}$ and $\bar{A}(a) = \bar{A}(b) = \bar{0}$. Clearly, $\bar{A}$ is an i-v fuzzy quasi-ideal of N .

3. An $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v Fuzzy Subnear-Rings and $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v Fuzzy Ideals:

In this section, we introduce the notions of an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ i-v fuzzy subnear-ring and an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ i-v fuzzy ideal of a near-ring.

Definition 3.1. 13 An i-v fuzzy point $x_{\bar{t}}$ is said to belong to (resp. be fuzzy quasi-coincident with) an i-v fuzzy subset $\bar{A}$, written as $x_{\bar{t}} \in \bar{A}$ (resp. $x_{\bar{t}} q \bar{A}$) if $\bar{A}(x) \geq \bar{t}$ (resp. $\bar{A}(x) + \bar{t} > \bar{1}$). $x_{\bar{t}} \in \bar{A}$ or $x_{\bar{t}} q \bar{A}$ will be denoted by $x_{\bar{t}} \in \vee q \bar{A}$. $x_{\bar{t}} \in \bar{A}, x_{\bar{t}} \in \vee q \bar{A}$ will respectively mean $x_{\bar{t}} \in \bar{A}$ and $x_{\bar{t}} \in \vee q \bar{A}$ do not hold.

Definition 3.2. 14 An i-v fuzzy subset $\bar{A}$ of a group G is said to be an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy subgroup of G if $\forall x, y \in G$ and $\bar{t}, \bar{r} \in D(0,1]$, (i) $x_{\bar{t}}, y_{\bar{r}} \in \bar{A} \Rightarrow (xy)_{\min(\bar{t}, \bar{r})} \in \vee q \bar{A}$, (ii) $x_{\bar{t}} \in \bar{A} \Rightarrow x_{\bar{t}}^{-1} \in \vee q \bar{A}$.

Remark 3.3. 15(I) The conditions (i) and (ii) of Definition 3.2 are respectively equivalent to

(i) $\bar{A}(xy) \geq \min\{\bar{A}(x), \bar{A}(y), 0.5\} \forall x, y \in G$ and (ii) $\bar{A}(x^{-1}) \geq \min\{\bar{A}(x), 0.5\} \forall x \in G$.

(ii) For any $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy subgroup $\bar{A}$ of G such that $\bar{A}(x) \geq 0.5$ for some $x \in G$, $\bar{A}(e) \geq 0.5$.

(iii) Note that if $\bar{A}$ is an i-v fuzzy subgroup of a group G , then $\bar{A}$ is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy subgroup of G . However, the converse is not necessarily true.

Remark 3.4.16 An i-v fuzzy subset $\bar{A}$ of a group G is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy subgroup of G if and only if the level subset $\bar{A}_{\bar{t}} = \{x \in G / \bar{A}(x) \geq \bar{t}\}$ is a subgroup of $G \forall \bar{t} \in D(0, 0.5]$. But the level subset $\bar{A}_{\bar{t}}, \bar{t} \in D(0.5, 1]$ may not be a subgroup of G . Here we define the notion of an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy subnear-ring of N .

Definition 3.5. 17 An i-v fuzzy subset $\bar{A}$ is said to be an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy subnear-ring of N if $\forall x, y \in N$ and $\bar{t}, \bar{r} \in D(0,1]$, (i) $x_{\bar{t}}, y_{\bar{r}} \in \bar{A} \Rightarrow (x+y)_{\min(\bar{t}, \bar{r})} \in \vee q \bar{A}$, (ii) $x_{\bar{t}} \in \bar{A} \Rightarrow (-x)_{\bar{t}} \in \vee q \bar{A}$.

(iii) $x_{\bar{t}}, y_{\bar{r}} \in \bar{A} \Rightarrow (xy)_{\min(\bar{t}, \bar{r})} \in \vee q \bar{A}$,

Lemma 3.6. 18 Let $\bar{A}$ be an i-v fuzzy subset of N and $\bar{t}, \bar{r} \in D(0,1]$. Then

(i) (ia) $x_t, y_r \in \bar{A} \Rightarrow (x+y)_{\min(\bar{t}, \bar{r})} \in \vee q \bar{A}$ if and only if

$$(1a) \bar{A}(x+y) \geq \min^i \{\bar{A}(x), \bar{A}(y), 0.5\}, \forall x, y \in N.$$

(ii) (ib) $x_t \in \bar{A} \Rightarrow (-x)_t \in \vee q \bar{A}$ if and only if

$$(1b) \bar{A}(-x) \geq \min^i \{\bar{A}(x), 0.5\}, \forall x \in N.$$

(iii) (ic) $x_t, y_r \in \bar{A} \Rightarrow (xy)_{\min(\bar{t}, \bar{r})} \in \vee q \bar{A}$ if and only if

$$(1c) \bar{A}(xy) \geq \min^i \{\bar{A}(x), \bar{A}(y), 0.5\}, \forall x, y \in N.$$

Proof. (ia $\Rightarrow$ 1a): Suppose that $x, y \in N$. We consider the following two cases:

(a) $\bar{A}(x) \wedge \bar{A}(y) < 0.5$, (b) $\bar{A}(x) \wedge \bar{A}(y) \geq 0.5$.

Case a: Assume that $\bar{A}(x+y) < \bar{A}(x) \wedge \bar{A}(y) \wedge 0.5$, which implies $\bar{A}(x+y) < \bar{t} < \bar{A}(x) \wedge \bar{A}(y)$. Then $x_t, y_r \in \bar{A}$, but $(x+y)_r \in \vee q \bar{A}$ which contradicts (ia).

Case b: Assume that $\bar{A}(x+y) < 0.5$, then $x_{0.5}, y_{0.5} \in \bar{A}$, but $(x+y)_{0.5} \in \vee q \bar{A}$, a contradiction. Hence (1a) holds.

(ib $\Rightarrow$ 1b): Suppose that $x \in N$. We consider the following cases: (a) $\bar{A}(x) < 0.5$, (b) $\bar{A}(x) \geq 0.5$.

Case a: Assume that $\bar{A}(x) = \bar{t} < 0.5$ and $\bar{A}(-x) = \bar{r} < \bar{A}(x)$. Choose $\bar{s}$ such that $\bar{r} < \bar{s} < \bar{t}$ and $\bar{r} + \bar{s} < \bar{1}$. Then $x_s \in \bar{A}$, but $(-x)_s \in \vee q \bar{A}$ which contradicts (ib). So $\bar{A}(-x) \geq \bar{A}(x) = \bar{A}(x) \wedge 0.5$.

Case b: Let $\bar{A} \geq 0.5$. If $\bar{A}(-x) < \bar{A} \wedge 0.5$, then $x_{0.5} \in \bar{A}$, but $(-x)_{0.5} \in \vee q \bar{A}$, which contradicts (ib). So $\bar{A}(-x) \geq \bar{A}(x) \wedge 0.5$. (ic) $\Rightarrow$ (1c): The proof is similar to (ia $\Rightarrow$ 1a.)

Theorem 3.7. 19 An i-v fuzzy subset $\bar{A}$ of N is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy subnear-ring of N if and only if (i) $\bar{A}(x-y) \geq \min^i \{\bar{A}(x), \bar{A}(y), 0.5\}, \forall x, y \in N$. (ii) $\bar{A}(xy) \geq \min^i \{\bar{A}(x), \bar{A}(y), 0.5\}, \forall x, y \in N$.

Proof. (i) Suppose that $x, y \in N$. We consider the following cases:

(a) $\bar{A}(x) \wedge \bar{A}(y) < 0.5$, (b) $\bar{A}(x) \wedge \bar{A}(y) \geq 0.5$.

Case a: Assume that $\bar{A}(x-y) < \bar{A}(x) \wedge \bar{A}(y) \wedge 0.5$, which implies $\bar{A}(x-y) < \bar{t} < \bar{A}(x) \wedge \bar{A}(y)$. Then $x_t, y_r \in \bar{A}$, but $(x-y)_r \in \vee q \bar{A}$ which contradicts $x_t, y_r \in \bar{A} \Rightarrow (x+y)_{\min(\bar{t}, \bar{r})} \in \vee q \bar{A}$.

Case b: Assume that $\bar{A}(x-y) < 0.5$. then $x_{0.5}, y_{0.5} \in \bar{A}$, but $(x-y)_{0.5} \in \vee q \bar{A}$, a contradiction. Hence $\bar{A}(x-y) \geq \min^i \{\bar{A}(x), \bar{A}(y), 0.5\}$ holds.

(ii) Suppose that $x, y \in N$. We consider the following cases:

(a) $\bar{A}(y) < 0.5$, (b) $\bar{A}(y) \geq 0.5$.

Case a: Assume that $\bar{A}(y) = \bar{t} < 0.5$ and $\bar{A}(xy) = \bar{r} < \bar{A}(x)$. Choose $\bar{s}$ such that $\bar{r} < \bar{s} < \bar{t}$ and $\bar{r} + \bar{s} < \bar{1}$. Then $y_s \in \bar{A}$, but $(xy)_s \in \vee q \bar{A}$ which contradicts $y_r \in \bar{A}$ and $x \in N$ implies $(xy)_r \in \vee q \bar{A}$. So $\bar{A}(xy) \geq \bar{A}(y) = \bar{A}(y) \wedge 0.5$.

Case b: Let $\bar{A}(y) \geq 0.5$. If $\bar{A}(xy) < \bar{A} \wedge 0.5$, then $y_{0.5} \in \bar{A}$, but $(xy)_{0.5} \in \vee q \bar{A}$, which contradicts $y_r \in \bar{A}$ and $x \in N$ implies $(xy)_r \in \vee q \bar{A}$. So $\bar{A}(xy) \geq \bar{A}(y) = \bar{A}(y) \wedge 0.5$.

Remark 3.8. 20 Every i-v fuzzy subnear-ring of N (according to Definition 2.8) is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy subnear-ring of N . But the converse is not necessarily true as shown by the following example.

Example 3.9. 21 Consider the near-ring $(N, +, \cdot)$ as defined in Example 2.12. Define an i-v fuzzy subset $\bar{A}: N \rightarrow [0, 1]$ by $\bar{A}(0) = 0.7, \bar{A}(a) = 0.4, \bar{A}(b) = 0.8, \bar{A}(c) = 0.4$. Then $\bar{A}$ is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ i-v fuzzy subnear-ring of N . But since $\bar{A}(0) = \bar{A}(b-b) \not\geq \min^i \{\bar{A}(b), \bar{A}(b)\}$, $\bar{A}$ is not an i-v fuzzy subnear-ring of N .

Definition 3.10. 22 An i-v fuzzy subset $\bar{A}$ of N is said to be an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy ideal of N if

- (i) $\bar{A}$ is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy subnear-ring of N .
- (ii) $x_i \in \bar{A} \Rightarrow (y+x-y)_i \in \vee q \bar{A} \forall x, y \in N$,
- (iii) $x_i \in \bar{A} \Rightarrow (xy)_i \in \vee q \bar{A} \forall x, y \in N$,
- (iv) $i_i \in \bar{A} \Rightarrow (x(y+i)-xy)_i \in \vee q \bar{A}$ for any $x, y, i \in N$. and $t \in (0,1]$

An i-v fuzzy subset $\bar{A}$ with conditions (i), (ii) and (iii) is called an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy right ideal of N . If $\bar{A}$ satisfies (i), (ii) and (iv), then it is called an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ i-v fuzzy left ideal of N .

Lemma 3.11. 23 Let $\bar{A}$ be an i-v fuzzy subset of N . Then

- (I) (a) $\bar{A}$ is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy subnear-ring of N and
 (b) $\bar{A}(x-y), \bar{A}(xy) \geq \min^i \{ \bar{A}(x), \bar{A}(y), 0.5 \} \forall x, y \in N$ are equivalent.
- (II) (c) $x_i \in \bar{A} \Rightarrow (y+x-y)_i \in \vee q \bar{A}$ and
 (d) $\bar{A}(y+x-y) \geq \min^i \{ \bar{A}(x), 0.5 \} \forall x, y \in N$ are equivalent.
- (III) (e) $x_i \in \bar{A} \Rightarrow (xy)_i \in \vee q \bar{A}$ and
 (f) $\bar{A}(xy) \geq \min^i \{ \bar{A}(x), 0.5 \} \forall x, y \in N$ are equivalent.
- (IV) (g) $i_i \in \bar{A} \Rightarrow (y(x+i)-yx)_i \in \vee q \bar{A}$ and
 (h) $\bar{A}(y(x+i)-yx) \geq \min^i \{ \bar{A}(i), 0.5 \}$ for any $x, y, i \in N$ are equivalent.

Proof. (a) $\Leftrightarrow$ (b) It follows from Theorem 3.7.

(c) $\Rightarrow$ (d) Let $x, y \in N$ and $\bar{A}(x) < 0.5$. Assume that $\bar{A}(y+x-y) < \bar{A}(x)$.

Choose $\bar{t}$ such that $\bar{A}(y+x-y) < \bar{t} \leq \bar{A}(x)$.

Then $x_i \in \bar{A}$ and $(y+x-y)_i \in \vee q \bar{A}$ which contradicts (c). Thus $\bar{A}(y+x-y) \geq \bar{A}(x)$.

Next, let $\bar{A}(x) \geq 0.5$. (1) Assume that $\bar{A}(y+x-y) < 0.5$. (2)

From (1) we have $x_{0.5} \in \bar{A}$. But from (2) we have $(y+x-y)_{0.5} \in \vee q \bar{A}$, a contradiction. Hence (d) holds. (d) $\Rightarrow$ (c) Let

$x_i \in \bar{A}$ and $y \in N$. Then $\bar{A}(x) \geq \bar{t}$. By (d),

$$\bar{A}(y+x-y) \geq \min^i \{ \bar{A}(x), 0.5 \} \geq \min^i \{ \bar{t}, 0.5 \}.$$

Then $\bar{A}(y+x-y) \geq \bar{t}$ if $\bar{t} \leq 0.5$ and $\bar{A}(y+x-y) \geq 0.5$ if $\bar{t} > 0.5$. Hence $(y+x-y)_i \in \vee q \bar{A}$. Thus (c) holds.

(e) $\Rightarrow$ (f) Assume that (e) is valid and let $x, y \in N$. Let $\bar{A}(x) < 0.5$. Assume that $\bar{A}(xy) < \bar{A}(x)$. Choose $\bar{t}$ such that $\bar{A}(xy) < \bar{t} \leq \bar{A}(x)$,

then $x_i \in \bar{A}$ and $(xy)_i \in \vee q \bar{A}$ which contradicts (e). So $\bar{A}(xy) \geq \bar{A}(x)$. Next, let $\bar{A}(x) \geq 0.5$. (3)

Assume that $\bar{A}(xy) < 0.5$. (4)

From (3), we have $x_{0.5} \in \bar{A}$. From (4), we have $(xy)_{0.5} \in \vee q \bar{A}$, which contradicts (e). Hence (f) holds.

(f) $\Rightarrow$ (e) Let $x_i \in \bar{A}$ and $y \in N$. By (f),

$$\bar{A}(xy) \geq \min^i \{ \bar{A}(x), 0.5 \} \geq \min^i \{ \bar{t}, 0.5 \}.$$

Then $\bar{A}(xy) \geq \bar{t}$ if $\bar{t} \leq 0.5$ and $\bar{A}(xy) \geq 0.5$ if $\bar{t} > 0.5$. Hence $(xy)_i \in \vee q \bar{A}$.

Thus (e) holds.

Similarly it can be shown that (g) and (h) are equivalent.

Theorem 3.12. 24 An i-v fuzzy subset $\bar{A}$ of N is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy ideal of N if and only if $\forall x, y, i \in N$,

- (i) $\bar{A}(x-y) \geq \min^i \{ \bar{A}(x), \bar{A}(y), 0.5 \}$,

$$(ii) \bar{A}(y+x-y) \geq \min^i \{\bar{A}(x), \bar{0.5}\},$$

$$(iii) \bar{A}(xy) \geq \min^i \{\bar{A}(x), \bar{0.5}\},$$

$$(iv) \bar{A}(y(x+i)-yx) \geq \min^i \{\bar{A}(i), \bar{0.5}\}.$$

Proof. The proof is straightforward from Lemma 3.11.

Remark 3.13 25 An i-v fuzzy ideal of N according to the Definition 2.9 is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy ideal of N . But the converse, in general, is not true as shown by the following example.

Example 3.14 26 Consider the $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy subnear-ring $\bar{A}$ of N as defined in example 3.9. Then $\bar{A}$ is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy ideal of N . But since $\bar{A}(0) = \bar{A}(b0) \not\geq \bar{A}(b)$, $\bar{A}$ is not an i-v fuzzy ideal of N .

Theorem 3.15 27 A non-empty subset I of N is a subnear-ring (ideal) of N if and only if $\bar{K}_I$ is a characteristic function an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy subnear-ring (ideal) of N .

Proof. We prove the result for ideals. Let I be an ideal of N . It is clear that $\bar{K}_I$ (characteristic function) is an i-v fuzzy ideal of N . By Remark 3.8, $\bar{K}_I$ is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy ideal of N .

Conversely, let $\bar{K}_I$ be an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy ideal of N . For any $x, y \in I$, we have

$$\bar{K}_I(x-y) \geq \min^i \{\bar{K}_I(x), \bar{K}_I(y), \bar{0.5}\} = \min\{1, 1, 0.5\} = 0.5,$$

and so $\bar{K}_I(x-y) = \bar{1}$. Thus $x-y \in I$. Let $a \in N$ and $x \in I$. Then

$$\bar{K}_I(a+x-a) \geq \min^i \{\bar{K}_I(x), \bar{0.5}\} = 0.5,$$

and thus $\bar{K}_I(a+x-a) = \bar{1}$. This shows that $a+x-a \in I$, and therefore $(I, +)$ is a normal subgroup of $(N, +)$. Now let $a \in N$ and $x \in I$. Then

$$\bar{K}_I(xa) \geq \min^i \{\bar{K}_I(x), \bar{0.5}\} = 0.5,$$

and so $xa \in I$. Finally let $a, b \in N$ and $i \in I$. Then

$$\bar{K}_I(a(b+i)-ab) \geq \min^i \{\bar{K}_I(i), \bar{0.5}\} = 0.5,$$

which implies that $a(b+i)-ab \in I$. Consequently, I is an ideal of N .

Theorem 3.16 28 29 An i-v fuzzy subset $\bar{A}$ of N is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy subnear-ring (ideal) of N if and only if the level subset $\bar{A}_t$ is a subnear-ring (ideal) of $N \forall 0 < t < 0.5$.

Proof. $\bar{A}(xy) \geq \min^i \{\bar{A}(x), \bar{A}(y), \bar{0.5}\} \geq \min^i \{t, t, \bar{0.5}\} = t$, oof. We prove the result in the case of $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy ideals. Let $\bar{A}$ be an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy ideal of N . Let $t \leq 0.5$ and $x, y, i \in \bar{A}_t$. Then

$$(i) \bar{A}(x-y) \geq \min^i \{\bar{A}(x), \bar{A}(y), \bar{0.5}\} = \min^i \{t, t, \bar{0.5}\} = t, \text{ and so } x-y \in \bar{A}_t.$$

$$(ii) \text{ and so } xy \in \bar{A}_t.$$

$$(iii) \bar{A}(y+x-y) \geq \min^i \{\bar{A}(x), \bar{0.5}\} \geq \min^i \{t, \bar{0.5}\} = t, \text{ and so } y+x-y \in \bar{A}_t.$$

$$(iv) \text{ For every } z \in N, \text{ we have } \bar{A}(xz) \geq \min^i \{\bar{A}(x), \bar{0.5}\} \geq \min^i \{t, \bar{0.5}\} = t, \text{ and so } xz \in \bar{A}_t.$$

$$(v) \text{ For every } a, b \in N, \text{ we have } \bar{A}(a(b+i)-ab) \geq \min^i \{\bar{A}(i), \bar{0.5}\} = \min^i \{t, \bar{0.5}\} = t, \text{ and thus } a(b+i)-ab \in \bar{A}_t.$$

So $\bar{A}_t$ is an ideal of N .

Conversely, let $\bar{A}_t$ be an ideal of $N \forall t \leq 0.5$. If possible, let there exist $x, y \in N$ such that

$$\bar{A}(x-y) < \min^i \{\bar{A}(x), \bar{A}(y), \bar{0.5}\}.$$

Choose t such that

$$\bar{A}(x-y) < t < \min^i \{\bar{A}(x), \bar{A}(y), \bar{0.5}\}.$$

Then $x, y \in \bar{A}_t$. Since $\bar{A}_t$ is an ideal of N , we have $x-y \in \bar{A}_t$. Thus $\bar{A}(x-y) \geq t$, a contradiction to our assumption. So $\bar{A}(x-y) \geq \min^i \{\bar{A}(x), \bar{A}(y), \bar{0.5}\} \forall x, y \in N$.

Similarly it can be shown that

$$\overline{A}(xy) \geq \min^i \{ \overline{A}(x), \overline{A}(y), 0.5 \},$$

$$\overline{A}(y+x-y) \geq \min^i \{ \overline{A}(x), 0.5 \},$$

$$\overline{A}(x(y+i)-xy) \geq \min^i \{ \overline{A}(i), 0.5 \},$$

$\forall x, y, i \in N$. Therefore, $\overline{A}$ is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ i-v fuzzy ideal of N .

Remark 3.17 3031 Let $\overline{A}$ be an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy subnear-ring (ideal) of N , then the level subset $\overline{A}_t$

may not be a subnear-ring(ideal) of $N \forall t \in D(0.5, 1]$. Since by Remark 3.4, $\overline{A}_t, t \in D(0.5, 1]$, may not be a subgroup of N .

4. An $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v Fuzzy Quasi-Ideals:

In this section, we introduce the notion of an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy quasi-ideal of a near-ring which is a generalization of $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy quasi-ideal of a near-ring.

Definition 4.1 3233 An $(\in, \in \vee q)$ i-v fuzzy subgroup $\overline{A}$ of N is called an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy quasi-ideal of N if $\forall x \in N$,

$$\overline{A}(x) \geq \min^i \{ ((\overline{A} \circ N) \cap (N \circ \overline{A}) \cap (N * \overline{A}))(x), 0.5 \}, \text{ that is, } \overline{A}(x) \geq \min^i \{ (\overline{A} \circ N)(x), (N \circ \overline{A})(x), (N * \overline{A})(x), 0.5 \}.$$

Remark 4.2 34 Every i-v fuzzy quasi-ideal (according to the Definition 3.11 of N is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy quasi-ideal of N . But the converse is not necessarily true as shown by the following example.

Example 4.3 35 Consider the set integer modulo 4, $Z_4 = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ with the following operations.

+	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	1	2	3	0
2	2	3	0	1
3	3	0	1	2

.	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	0	2	0	1
2	0	2	0	3
3	0	0	0	2

Clearly $(Z_4, +, \cdot)$ is a near-ring. Let an i-v fuzzy subset

$\overline{A}: Z_4 \rightarrow D[0, 1]$ be defined by $\overline{A}(0) = 0.6, \overline{A}(1) = 0.4, \overline{A}(2) = 0.8, \overline{A}(3) = 0.4$. Then $\overline{A}$ is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy quasi-ideal of Z_4 . But $\overline{A}$ is not an i-v fuzzy quasi-ideal of Z_4 .

Since $\overline{A}(0) \not\geq \min^i \{ (\overline{A} \circ N)(0), (N \circ \overline{A})(0), (N * \overline{A})(0) \}$.

Remark 4.4 36 If $\overline{Q}$ is a quasi-ideal of N , then $\overline{K_Q}$ is an i-v fuzzy quasi-ideal and also an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy quasi-ideal of N .

Theorem 4.5 37 A non-empty i-v fuzzy subset $\overline{Q}$ of N is a quasi-ideal of N if and only if $\overline{K_Q}$ is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy quasi-ideal of N .

Proof. Let $\overline{Q}$ be a quasi-ideal of N . $\overline{K_Q}$ is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy quasi-ideal of N .

conversely, let $\overline{K_Q}$ be an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy quasi-ideal of N . Let a be any element of $\overline{Q}N \cap N\overline{Q} \cap N * \overline{Q}$. Then there exist element c, x, y of N and elements b, i of $\overline{Q}$ such that $a = bc = x(y+i) - xy$. Now we have

$$(\overline{K_Q} \circ N)(a) = \sup_{a=pq} [\min^i \{ \overline{K_Q}(p), N(q) \}] \geq \min^i \{ \overline{K_Q}(b), N(c) \} = \min \{ \bar{1}, \bar{1} \} = \bar{1}.$$

So $(\overline{K_Q} \circ N)(a) = \bar{1}$. Similarly, $(N \circ \overline{K_Q})(a) = \bar{1}$. Moreover, $(N * \overline{K_Q})(a) = (N * \overline{K_Q})(x(y+i) - xy) \geq \overline{K_Q}(i) = \bar{1}$.

Hence, $\overline{K_Q}(a) \geq \min^i \{ (\overline{K_Q} \circ N)(a), (N \circ \overline{K_Q})(a), (N * \overline{K_Q})(a), 0.5 \} = 0.5$, and so $\overline{K_Q}(a) = \bar{1}$ which means $a \in \overline{Q}$.

Therefore $\overline{Q}N \cap N\overline{Q} \cap N * \overline{Q} \subseteq \overline{Q}$. Hence $\overline{Q}$ is a quasi-ideal of N .

Remark 4.6 38 Note that in general an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy quasi-ideal in a near-ring N is not an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy subnear-ring of N . In fact, we obtain an example of an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy quasi-ideal which is not an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy subnear-ring and obtain conditions for an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy quasi-ideal in a near-ring to be an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy subnear-ring.

Example 4.7 39 Consider the non-zero-symmetric near-ring $(N, +, \cdot)$ as defined in Example . Define an i-v fuzzy subset $\bar{A}: N \rightarrow D[0, 1]$ by $\bar{A}(0) = 0.7, \bar{A}(a) = 0.3 = \bar{A}(b), \bar{A}(c) = 0.6$. Then $\bar{A}$ is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy quasi-ideal of N . But since $\bar{A}(a) = \bar{A}(ca) \not\geq \min^i\{\bar{A}(c), \bar{A}(a), 0.5\}$, $\bar{A}$ is not an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy subnear-ring of N .

Theorem 4.8 40 Every $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy quasi-ideal in a zero-symmetric near-ring is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy subnear-ring.

Proof. Let $\bar{A}$ be an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy quasi-ideal in a zero-symmetric near-ring N . Choose $a, b, c, x, y, i \in N$ such that $a = bc = x(y+i) - xy$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{A}(a) &\geq \min^i\{(\bar{A} \circ N)(a), (N \circ \bar{A})(a), (N * \bar{A})(a), 0.5\} \\ &= \min^i\{sup_{a=bc}^i[\min^i\{\bar{A}(b), N(c)\}], sup_{a=bc}^i[\min^i\{N(b), \bar{A}(c)\}], sup_{a=x(y+i)-xy}^i\{A(i), 0.5\}\} \\ &\geq \min^i\{sup_{a=bc}^i[\min^i\{\bar{A}(b), N(c)\}], sup_{a=bc}^i[\min^i\{N(b), \bar{A}(c)\}], sup_{a=b(0+c)-b0}^i\{\bar{A}(c), 0.5\}\} \\ &= \min^i\{sup \bar{A}(b), sup \bar{A}(c), sup \bar{A}(c), 0.5\} \end{aligned}$$

since N is zero-symmetric

$$\geq \min^i\{\bar{A}(b), \bar{A}(c), 0.5\}.$$

Therefore $\bar{A}(bc) \geq \min\{\bar{A}(b), \bar{A}(c), 0.5\}$. Hence $\bar{A}$ is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy subnear-ring of N .

Theorem 4.9 41 Every $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy right ideal of N is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy quasi-ideal of N .

Proof. Let $\bar{A}$ be an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy right ideal of N . Choose $a, b, c, x, y, i \in N$,

such that $a = bc = x(y+i) - xy$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} &((\bar{A} \circ N) \cap (N \circ \bar{A}) \cap (N * \bar{A}))(a) \\ &= \min^i\{(\bar{A} \circ N)(a), (N \circ \bar{A})(a), (N * \bar{A})(a)\} \\ &= \min^i\{sup_{a=bc}^i\{\min^i\{\bar{A}(b), N(c)\}\}, sup_{a=bc}^i\{\min^i\{N(b), \bar{A}(c)\}\}, (N * \bar{A})(x(y+i) - xy)\} \\ &(\text{Since } N(z) = 1 \forall z \in N) \\ &= \min^i\{sup^i \bar{A}(b), \bar{A}(c), (N * \bar{A})(x(y+i) - xy)\}. (5) \end{aligned}$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} &= \min^i\{((\bar{A} \circ N) \cap (N \circ \bar{A}) \cap (N * \bar{A}))(a), 0.5\} \\ &= \min^i\{\min^i\{sup \bar{A}(b), sup \bar{A}(c), (N * \bar{A})(x(y+i) - xy)\}, 0.5\} \\ &= \min^i\{\min^i\{sup \bar{A}(b), 0.5\}, sup \bar{A}(c), (N * \bar{A})(x(y+i) - xy)\} \\ &(\text{since } \bar{A} \text{ is an } (\in, \in \vee q) \text{ - i-v fuzzy right ideal, } \bar{A}(bc) \geq \min^i\{\bar{A}(b), 0.5\}) \\ &\leq \min^i\{\bar{A}(bc), N(c), N(x(y+i) - xy)\} = \bar{A}(bc). \end{aligned}$$

Thus $\bar{A}(a) \geq \min^i\{((\bar{A} \circ N) \cap (N \circ \bar{A}) \cap (N * \bar{A}))(a), 0.5\}$. So, $\bar{A}$ is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy quasi-ideal of N .

Theorem 4.10 42 Every $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy left ideal of N is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy quasi-ideal of N .

Proof. Let $\bar{A}$ be an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy left ideal of N . Choose $a, b, c, x, y, i \in N$, such that $a = bc = x(y+i) - xy$.

$$\begin{aligned} &((\bar{A} \circ N) \cap (N \circ \bar{A}) \cap (N * \bar{A}))(a) \\ &= \min^i\{sup^i \bar{A}(b), \bar{A}(c), (N * \bar{A})(x(y+i) - xy)\} (by(5)) \\ &= \min^i\{sup^i \bar{A}(b), sup^i \bar{A}(c), sup^i \bar{A}(i)\} (6) \end{aligned}$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} &= \min^i\{((\bar{A} \circ N) \cap (N \circ \bar{A}) \cap (N * \bar{A}))(a), 0.5\} \\ &= \min^i\{\min^i\{sup^i \bar{A}(b), sup^i \bar{A}(c), sup^i \bar{A}(i)\}, 0.5\} \\ &= \min^i\{\min^i\{sup^i \bar{A}(b), sup^i \bar{A}(c), \min^i\{sup^i \bar{A}(i), 0.5\}\} \\ &(\text{since } \bar{A} \text{ is an } (\in, \in \vee q) \text{ - i-v fuzzy left ideal, } \bar{A}(x(y+i) - xy) \geq \min^i\{\bar{A}(i), 0.5\}) \\ &\leq \min^i\{N(b), N(c), \bar{A}(x(y+i) - xy)\} = \bar{A}(x(y+i) - xy) = \bar{A}(a). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $\bar{A}(a) \not\geq \min\{((\bar{A} \circ N) \cap (N \circ \bar{A}) \cap (N * \bar{A}))(a), 0.5\}$. Hence $\bar{A}$ is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy quasi-ideal of N .

Theorem 4.11 43 Every $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy ideal of N is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ - i-v fuzzy quasi-ideal of N . The proof is straight forward from Theorem 4.9 and Theorem 4.10

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